

BUSINESS GUARANTEE IN ISLAMIC ECONOMICS

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Abstract

The business guarantee (*el-kefale*) represents one of the fundamental institutes of Islamic law of obligations and an important mechanism for securing the fulfilment of obligations in business and financial relationships. Its essence lies in the voluntary assumption of responsibility by the guarantor (*kefil*) for the obligations of the principal debtor, thereby protecting the rights of creditors and strengthening trust between contracting parties. This institute has a firm foundation in the Quran, the Sunnah of the Prophet of Allah (pbuh), as well as in the consensus of Islamic jurists, which confirms its legal validity and permanent applicability. The paper analyses the linguistic and terminological meaning of the business guarantee, its Sharia-legal bases, conditions of validity, constitutive elements, and types, with a special emphasis on the difference between personal and material guarantees. It also considers the positions of different Islamic legal schools regarding the permissibility and scope of the guarantor's liability, especially in the context of financial obligations and violations. Special attention is paid to contemporary applications of the business guarantee through the decisions of international Sharia institutions, including the International Islamic Fiqh Academy of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC). In conclusion, the paper indicates that the business guarantee in the Islamic economy does not represent merely a legal instrument for securing obligations, but also an ethical mechanism that contributes to legal certainty, the stability of business relations, and the realization of the objectives of Islamic law (*Maqasid al-Shari'ah*) in the contemporary economic environment.

Keywords: business guarantee, *el-kefale*, Islamic law, Islamic economy, suretyship, contractual relations, Sharia regulations

INTRODUCTION

Modern economic and business relations, characterized by complex contractual structures and increased financial risks, impose a need for efficient mechanisms to secure the rights of contracting parties. One of the key instruments of legal and economic security in Islamic law is the business guarantee (*el-kefale*), which represents a form of voluntary assumption of responsibility for the obligations of another entity. This institute is deeply rooted in the Quran, the Sunnah of the Prophet (pbuh), and the consensus of classical Islamic jurists, confirming its legal validity and practical relevance across different historical and social contexts.

The business guarantee in Islamic law is not merely a technical legal mechanism, but also an expression of ethical responsibility, solidarity, and social cohesion. Its

purpose is reflected in the protection of creditors' rights, the facilitation of business transactions, and the strengthening of trust among participants in economic relations, while simultaneously respecting Sharia principles of justice and the prohibition of injustice. Precisely because of this, *kefala* occupies an important place in the field of Islamic law of obligations and the modern Islamic economy.

The aim of this paper is to consider, through a descriptive-analytical approach, the concept of the business guarantee, its Sharia-legal foundations, validity conditions, constitutive elements, and types, as well as the differences in the views of Islamic legal schools. Special attention is dedicated to the distinction between personal and material guarantees, their legal treatment, and practical application in contemporary business frameworks, including relevant decisions of modern Sharia institutions. In this way, the paper seeks to contribute to a better understanding of this institute and its significance in building a stable and ethically grounded Islamic economic system.

LINGUISTIC MEANING OF *EL-KEFALE*

In a linguistic sense, the business guarantee (*el-kefale*) signifies joining, connecting, or taking something upon oneself. In an economic and business context, this term refers to assuming responsibility for the obligations of another entity, whereby the guarantor connects themselves to the principal debtor regarding the fulfillment of the obligation. From this root stems the Quranic usage of the term, in which Allah Almighty describes the act of placing something under one's protection and care.

"**And Zakariya took charge of her**" (Qur'an: 3:37) meaning he took her under his direct responsibility and ensured her safety and security.

This meaning aligns with the statement of the Prophet (pbuh), which points to assuming an obligation and guaranteeing for another, representing the fundamental function of a guarantor in business and financial relations. Sahl ibn Sa'd (r.a.) narrates that the Prophet (pbuh) said: "'I and the guardian (protector) of an orphan will be in Paradise like this (close).'" And he pointed with his index and middle fingers. " (Bukhari, 5659)

In Sharia legal terminology, "*kefala*" (suretyship) is defined as: the joining of the guarantor's responsibility to the obligations of the principal debtor, so that the creditor may collect from any party guaranteeing the fulfilment of the obligation.

In business and financial practice, the following types of guarantees are distinguished:

- **Personal guarantee:** When the guarantor assumes the obligation that a certain person will fulfil their duty or appear before a competent authority (e.g., guarantee for presence in a procedure or the return of a detained person).
- **Financial guarantee:** When the guarantor guarantees that they will settle a monetary obligation on behalf of the debtor if the debtor fails to make payment within the foreseen period; this is equivalent to a performance guarantee or payment guarantee.
- **Guarantee of proper execution and return of property:** When the guarantor assumes responsibility that the user of rented, borrowed, or

available property will return it within the agreed period and in the prescribed condition; in modern practice, this resembles a guarantee for the return of leased items.

SHARIA-LEGAL STATUS OF THE BUSINESS GUARANTEE

The business guarantee (*el-kefale*) represents a legally valid and fully permissible instrument in Islamic law. Its application and legal force are confirmed by authoritative sources, the Quran, the Sunnah, and the unanimous position of competent Islamic jurists.

Allah Almighty in the Quran points to the principle of assuming responsibility and ensuring the fulfillment of obligations, which forms the fundamental basis for the legitimacy of this institute in financial and business relations.

"So her Lord accepted her with good acceptance and caused her to grow in a good manner and put her in the care of Zakariya." (Qur'an, 3:37)

In another Quranic verse, Allah Almighty further confirms this legal principle, pointing to the obligation of reliably executing assumed obligations and protecting the rights of participants in business relations.

"And for he who produces it is [the reward of] a camel's load, and I am responsible (a guarantor) for it." (Qur'an, 12:72)

As previously stated, the business guarantee in Islamic law has a firm basis in the Sunnah of the Prophet (pbuh), where the permissibility of assuming responsibility for the obligations of another and protecting the rights of contracting parties is clearly indicated.

- Abu Umamah (r.a.) narrates that the Prophet (pbuh) said: "The guarantor (one who guarantees in business ventures) is the one who is responsible." (Musnad Ahmad, 22349)
- Sahl ibn Sa'd (r.a.) narrates that the Prophet (pbuh) said: "'I and the guardian (protector) of an orphan are in Paradise like this (close).'" And he pointed with his index and middle fingers." (Bukhari, 5659)
- Salama ibn al-Akwa (r.a.) narrates that a funeral procession was brought to the Prophet (pbuh) for him to pray over it, and he asked: "Did he have any debt?" They said: "No." So, he prayed over him. Then another funeral was brought, and he asked: "Did he have any debt?" They said: "Yes." He said: "Pray over your companion." Abu Qatada said: "I assume his debt, O Messenger of Allah!", and then he prayed over him (Bukhari, 2173).

CONDITIONS OF THE BUSINESS GUARANTEE

Islamic jurists have defined the following conditions for the validity and legitimacy of a business guarantee:

- **Object of the guarantee:** The guarantee can only relate to a person or property that is actually transferable or available for the fulfillment of the obligation.

- **Nature of the obligation:** The debt or obligation must be clearly defined and of such a nature that its execution can be demanded.
- **Enforceability of the obligation:** The debt must be real and inalienable, meaning it cannot be written off except by its actual settlement or official release.
- **Capacity of the guarantor:** The *kefil* (guarantor) must have the capacity, financial means, or authority to assume and fulfill the obligation they are guaranteeing.

CONSTITUTIVE ELEMENTS OF THE BUSINESS GUARANTEE

According to Hanafi jurists, the business guarantee consists of one key constitutive element—the constructive form (offer and acceptance, i.e., *Ijab* and *Qabul*). The offer comes from the guarantor, while the acceptance comes from the creditor. Conversely, Shafi'i jurists consider that the fulfillment of five constitutive elements is required for the validity of a business guarantee contract.

The Shafi'i elements are:

- **Guarantor (*el-kefil*):** The person assuming responsibility and guaranteeing the execution of the obligation.
- **Creditor (*el-mekful lehu*):** The person who has the right to collect or protect their claims.
- **Obligation or Debt (*el-mekful bihi*):** The actual, enforceable obligation that is the subject of the guarantee.
- **Debtor or Protégé (*el-mekful 'anhu*):** The person whose obligations are being guaranteed.
- **Constructive Form (*es-siga*):** The formal legal procedure by which the guarantee contract is established and confirmed, including offer and acceptance.

This structure enables a clear distribution of responsibilities and rights among all involved parties in financial and business relations.

TYPES OF BUSINESS GUARANTEE

In Sharia law, two basic types of business guarantees are recognized:

- **Material (Property) Guarantee:** A guarantee secured by property or concrete assets.
- **Personal Guarantee:** A guarantee in which a physical person assumes responsibility with their own being, i.e., life or personal obligation.

PERSONAL GUARANTEE

In Sharia law, a personal guarantee implies that the guarantor (*kefil*) assumes the obligation to ensure the presence of the debtor or the person they are guaranteeing for before the creditor or a competent authority, should the person violate the law or

contractual provisions. In this case, the object of the guarantee (obligation) and the debtor are fully connected, that is, the guarantee directly relates to the debtor's conduct or execution, and the guarantor assumes the responsibility to ensure its fulfillment.

The constructive form of a personal guarantee is based on a clear and formal statement by the guarantor, in which they assume full responsibility for the execution of the debtor's obligation. In Sharia law, this statement might read: "I guarantee for this man fully, with soul and body". The rule allows the guarantor to assume responsibility using expressions symbolizing total commitment, such as guaranteeing certain vital body parts (e.g., head, neck, face, body, and soul) or vital organs (heart, brain, liver). Conversely, it is not customary to use body parts whose function is not vital for life (e.g., hand, leg, eye, ear). This approach ensures legal clarity and the seriousness of the guarantor's obligation, a view shared by Shafi'i and Hanbali jurists, confirming its applicability in formal business relations.

There is a consensus among Islamic jurists that the personal business guarantee is a legally valid and legitimate instrument. This position is shared by Hanafi, Maliki, Shafi'i, and Hanbali scholars. Their legal basis rests on Quranic principles, where Allah emphasizes the obligation of assuming responsibility.

"[Yakub] said, 'Never will I send him with you until you give me a promise by Allah that you will bring him [back] to me, unless you should be surrounded by enemies.'" (Qur'an, 12:66)

This is further confirmed by the Sunnah of the Prophet (pbuh), where the principle of responsibility is emphasized, which makes a personal guarantee legitimate in financial and business transactions.

Abu Zanad narrated from Muhammad ibn Hamza ibn Aslami, who in turn narrated from his father. His father had been appointed by Umar (r.a.) as a zakat collector. During this time, a man had previously committed intercourse with his wife's slave. Hamza took responsibility for this man and brought him before Umar (r.a.). Umar had already ordered that the man be given 100 lashes, which he confirmed. However, Umar excused the man because he was unaware of the ruling.

Additionally, regarding converts, it is narrated: "Ask them to repent and take a guarantee from them!" Then they repented, and their families guaranteed for them. (Bukhari, 2168)

Islamic scholars divide personal guarantees into two basic categories:

1. **Guarantee for financial obligations:** When the guarantor assumes personal responsibility for a debtor who owes money or material assets to a creditor. This form is universally considered a legitimate and valid instrument in business transactions.
2. **Guarantee for offenses or violation of law:** When the guarantor assumes responsibility for an offender who has violated Sharia regulations or the law.

Regarding the second category, scholars distinguish between sins against the rights of Allah and sins against the rights of other people.

- **Rights of People:** The first tendency (Hanafi and Shafi'i jurists) holds that it is permissible to assume a personal guarantee for an accused person who has violated the rights of others (e.g., causing damage, homicide).

- **Rights of Allah:** The second tendency holds that personal guarantee is invalid and illegitimate when the accused has violated the rights of Allah (e.g., penalties for alcohol consumption, adultery). In this context, Hanafi, Shafi'i, and Hanbali jurists agree that personal guarantees are not valid here, as responsibility for sins against Allah's regulations cannot be the subject of a guarantee.

Note: Hanbali jurists further maintain that even the first type of personal guarantee, namely, a guarantee for violations against the rights of other individuals, is neither valid nor legitimate under Sharia. Their position is based on a hadith of the Prophet (peace be upon him), which emphasizes the impossibility of assuming responsibility for sins committed in contravention of Allah's commands.

This approach reflects the principle in Sharia law that the legal validity of a guarantee depends on the nature of the obligation and the type of liability involved. Such distinctions are essential for ensuring legal certainty and ethical predictability in financial and commercial transactions.

ʿAmr ibn Shuʿayb reported from his father, who reported from his grandfather, that the Prophet (peace and blessings be upon him) said: *“There is no guarantee or surety in matters of punishments.”* (Al-Bayhaqi, 11199)

From the cited hadith, it is evident that the Prophet (peace be upon him) prohibited the assumption of responsibility by a guarantor (*kafil*) in the context of criminal proceedings and the execution of punishments for violations against Allah's commands. Hanbali jurists further support their position with a rational argument, stating that it is illogical and unacceptable to require a guarantor (*kafil*) to bear the consequences of another person's actions, namely, the *makfūl ʿanhu* (the accused), if that individual fails to appear or fulfill his obligation regarding the implementation of the punishment.

According to this principle, the legal validity of a guarantee in Islamic law is directly tied to the nature of the obligation and the subject of liability. This distinction is essential for safeguarding legal certainty and ensuring fairness in financial and commercial transactions.

Consequently, the opinion of the Hanbali jurists may be regarded as closest to the Sharia truth, since it aligns with the Qur'anic principle: *“...And every soul earns not [blame] except against itself, and no bearer of burdens will bear the burden of another.”* (Qur'an, 6:164) This confirms that responsibility cannot be transferred to a third party for actions that he himself has not committed.

MATERIAL BUSINESS GUARANTEE

In Sharia law, a material business guarantee is defined as the guarantor assuming responsibility for the debt of another person, whereby the debtor remains primarily responsible for fulfilling their obligation. In other words, it is a financial instrument where the guarantor guarantees the fulfillment of the debtor's obligation via their material assets, ensuring creditor protection and legal security.

Material business guarantee is a valid and legitimate instrument, confirmed by the Sunnah and consensus of scholars. Unlike personal guarantees, Sharia jurists have

not strictly defined the formal business form of material guarantees. It can be established in various ways, such as explicit statements: "I guarantee his debt with the amount of one thousand euros" or "I guarantee for everything you buy in this business venture".

A key condition is the validity of the debt. A debt is considered valid if the debtor can be released from it only by full settlement or if the creditor decides to waive the collection. Islamic scholars (Hanafis, Malikis, Shafi'is, and Hanbalis) agree that the nature, form, and quantity of the debt are not conditions for the validity of a material guarantee. This is because *kefalet* functions on the principle of solidarity and voluntary assumption of obligation. For example, a guarantor can say: "I guarantee you for what the debtor owes" or "I guarantee for what you sell to Ahmed," even if the debt amount is unknown. However, a view attributed to Imam Shafi'i (partially accepted by others) suggests such a guarantee is not valid because the guarantor must know the type and quantity of the debt to avoid legal uncertainty.

All scholars agree that the debt must be an actual obligation of the debtor. If the debt does not represent a real obligation, the guarantee is not valid.

The guarantor is released from obligations in the following situations:

1. **Settlement of obligations:** When the main debtor fully settles the debt.
2. **Creditor's decision:** If the creditor explicitly releases the guarantor (e.g., "You have no further obligations").
3. **Release or prolongation for the debtor:** If the creditor releases the main debtor or grants a prolongation, the guarantor is released or the deadline is proportionally extended for them as well.

These principles ensure that the guarantor's responsibility is directly linked to the debtor's actual obligation, thereby preserving legal certainty, predictability, and fairness in financial and commercial transactions in a manner consistent with Sharia.

TERMINATION OF BUSINESS GUARANTEE

The business guarantee terminates in the following situations:

- **Surrender of the debtor:** When the debtor surrenders to authorities or the creditor.
- **Release of the guarantor:** If the creditor releases the guarantor from claims.
- **Death of the debtor:** If the debtor dies, the guarantor's obligations cease (unlike the death of the creditor, where obligations remain).
- **Settlement of debt:** When the debt is fully paid.
- **Release of the main debtor:** If the debtor is released from the debt, the guarantor is automatically released.

DECISION NO. 148 (16/6) – BUSINESS (COMMERCIAL) GUARANTEE

The International Islamic Fiqh Academy of the OIC, at its 16th session in Dubai (2005), issued a decision regulating business and trade guarantees.

1. Definition In a Sharia context, a business guarantee implies the guarantor assuming responsibility relative to the debtor to ensure debt settlement or the execution of other legal responsibilities. *Note:* This differs from "commercial sponsorship" (licenses), where a citizen may transfer or assign a business license to a non-citizen for business activities.

2. Main Forms of Commercial Guarantee (Sponsorship)

- **Assigning a license to a non-citizen:** The citizen allows the non-citizen to use the license for independent activity. The non-citizen finances the project entirely, and the citizen appears formally as the owner.
- **Joint use of license (Partnership):** The citizen participates with the non-citizen, earning fixed or periodic income. The non-citizen contributes capital and labor, and profit/loss is distributed according to agreement.

3. Sharia Status and Conditions

- **Assigning license without financial obligation:** Considered innovative; not a traditional guarantee. The right can be transferred with or without compensation, provided there is no deception or legal violation.
- **Joint use with contribution:** Implemented through financial contribution or license assignment with fair valuation. Profit and loss are shared according to agreement, making the transaction Sharia-valid.

4. Recommendations The Committee recommends that the OIC support the development of a common Islamic market, facilitate the free movement of capital, goods, services, and labor, and improve trade among Islamic countries.

CONCLUSION

Based on the foregoing, it can be concluded that the business guarantee (*el-kefale*) represents one of the fundamental and legally legitimate instruments of Islamic law of obligations, confirmed by the Quran, Sunnah, and consensus of jurists. Its essence lies in the voluntary assumption of responsibility to protect the rights of others, achieving legal certainty, business stability, and social solidarity. The analysis of different types shows that Islamic law offers a flexible normative framework adaptable to various business situations. The distinction between personal and material guarantees, and their permissibility regarding the nature of the obligation, indicates the precision and ethical consistency of the Sharia legal system. It is particularly significant to emphasize that responsibility cannot be transferred in matters relating exclusively to the rights of Allah, confirming the balance between justice and individual moral responsibility. Contemporary decisions by bodies like the OIC Fiqh Academy confirm the relevance of this institute, showing that Islamic law is a dynamic framework capable of responding to modern challenges. Thus, the business guarantee is not only a legal tool but a mechanism for building trust and ethical responsibility in business relations.

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